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THE ABILITY OF THE TEACHER TO APPLY THE TECHNOLOGIES OF INDIVIDUAL WORK WHEN TEACHING STUDENTS THE LESSONS OF SKILLFUL PAINTING

Temirova Muqaddas Ibragimjon qizi

Namangan State University

Teacher of the faculty "art studies"

muqaddas1407@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The article fully describes the art of monumental painting as well as the centuries-old significance of this art in Uzbekistan. In the process of coverage, attention was paid to the fact that today the continuing teacher understands the traditions of the student and the importance of effective organization of lesson processes using educational technologies for students.

Introduction: if we look at history, then the great norms of our ancestors in our country are quite obvious. We also have beautiful and elegantly decorated historical buildings that are also known around the world in the field of architecture. Of course, architects, craftsmen, Masters and artists showed their art in the decoration of these buildings. Especially popular is the ancient monumental color pictorial work of artists.

Results : Color-Image is a type of Fine Art and is a work of art that is created on a solid surface in colored materials, with the help of paints. Reality is an important tool for artistic depiction and interpretation of reality and influencing the viewer's thoughts and feelings, an important social content and a colorful ideological task. Including the art of the image of the majestic color.

The meaning of the word mahabatli gives the meaning that it is very large. And the monumental painting is considered to be large drawings on the inner or outer wall of buildings. Themes for monumental paintings are chosen with great importance. For this, historical events, heroic feats, folk tales, etc. are chosen. The style and figurative unity of monumental painting and architecture is important here. Monumental painting reflects significant events and phenomena, deep philosophical concepts taken from the life of society. Since it is intended to be seen from afar, an attempt is made to describe images in a generalizing way, to use smaller parts less. Colors also get somewhat conditional. Moreover, works of art have evolved in different countries, including the territory of Uzbekistan since very ancient times and have been processed into ancient manuscripts. Also, this type of art of the personality society has an independent content of works that have been widely used since ancient times, and the imagination of society is reflected in them. It is known from the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people that folk applied decorative art forms the main part of our cultural heritage. The types of applied art that arose and flourished in the Uzbek land

are world famous for their bemisil and uniqueness . Thinking about this stage of development, we witness that the origin of Uzbek applied decorative art began in the early period of mankind. The art of the Uzbek people has an ancient history that has been formed over the centuries. Works of monumental decorative art in Uzbekistan are one of the most popular and popular types of Fine Art. The reason is that this type of sculpture, decoration and Paintings will always be in the eyes of people colors are also somewhat conditional, nevertheless it should give a real picture of being. Monumental painting also serves as a decoration in architecture in a certain amount, which is why it is sometimes ²also called monumental - decorative painting. Mahabatli's works are divided into several types, in turn, depending on the method of execution. These are: frescoes, mosaics and Panno. Fresco - painting is a method of creating works in paints with the addition of aqueous or lime water, which, when drying the works in a new wet plaster, forms a thin layer of transparent calcium carbonate. This ensures that the paints are strengthened and the Fresco is kept long Mosaic-an image, pattern made from the same or different raw materials (tiles, stone, yogoch, marble, metal, etc.) slurry. Of the main types of monumental decorative art. Basically, in the decoration of buildings, works of Applied Art, workbench. art is used in the creation of works.

Panno-an image bounded by a pattern line or an exaggerated border, an exaggerated image, a piece of wall with embroidery and a painting designed for a special place, or an exaggerated image (relief). It is known to us that on the territory of Uzbekistan, from ancient times, construction work and architecture developed at an unprecedented level. Especially skillful color can not say the art of the image. Fine art developed perfectly during the reign of Amir Timur and his descendants. That is, great creative work was carried out in Samarkand, Tashkent, Bukhara, Shahrisabz, Karshi, Turkestan, Herat, Mashhad, Nishopur, Kabul and similar cities . Of course, Amir Timur first of ³all wanted to turn his capital Samarkand into the most beautiful and prosperous city in the world, and we can safely say that he realized this desire, because during the reign of Amir Timur, the city of Samarkand was an epic . The ruler turned the surroundings of his capital into gardens. In addition, the "White Palace" in Shahrisabz was the most magnificent and unique structure of its time, with a complex architectural solution. This beautiful palace was described by the most skillful masters using the art of a monumental Color Image

Although several hundred years have passed, the structures built by Amir Timur and the Timurids are one of the original masterpieces of World Architecture with their skill and beauty. Architecture ⁴of the Timur period, new techniques for decorating mahogany color

¹ Amanullaev, A. (2022). SPECIFIC FACTORS OF COMPREHENSIVE STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF THE HISTORY AND CULTURE OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(02), 1-4.

² Boltaboyevich, B. B., & Shokirjonugli, S. M. (2020). Formation of creative competences of the fine art future teachers describing geometrical forms (on sample of pencil drawing lessons). ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 10(5), 1996-2001.

³ Байметов, Б., & Шарипжонов, М. (2020). ОЛИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТАЪЛИМДА ТАЛАБАЛАР ИЖОДИЙ ҚОБИЛИЯТЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШДА ИНДИВИДУАЛ ТАЪЛИМ БЕРИШ МЕТОДИКАСИ (ҚАЛАМТАСВИР МИСОЛИДА). Academic research in educational sciences, (4), 357-363

⁴ Байметов, Б. Б., & Шарипжонов, М. Ш. (2020). ТАСВИРИЙ САНЪАТДАН МАЛАКАЛИ ПЕДАГОГ КАДРЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШДА НАЗАРИЙ ВА АМАЛИЙ МАШҲУЛОТЛАРНИНГ УЙҒУНЛИГИ. ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ, (SI-2№ 3).

even more with the art of the image boyitildi. Me the technology of decorations used in Mori monuments, while great skill and money were required, each detail means a pictorial meaning. Among the types of decoration widely used in the Q adimgı period, architecture ceramics and monumental painting, as well as wood and stone carving, developed.

During the Ulugbek period, the interior interiors of the buildings began to be decorated with a monumental pattern. Ganch, plant-shaped and geometric patterns on the surface of the walls were treated with glue colors. Most of the compositions were occupied by elements of a gilded pattern. Such officials made the territory of Uzbekistan very popular. When we look at the art of ancient monumental color images, artists can't help but tell the breadth of the world of imagination, man.

Painting is the art of color. Painting is one of the types of fine art that reflects real life and influences the thoughts and feelings of tamoshabin. A work of art performed on a surface of a satchel, with paints (watermark, tempera, watercolor, gouache, etc.) is called painting. The images in the painting are very bright and tomashabop. Artists create their works with painting and plastic tools. With the fact that they take advantage of the possibilities of pencil and composition, one of the most basic influencers in painting is color. Images in painting are created using paints that form a continuous layer of paint on the pictorial SATX. 2. in the calligraphic watercolor painting even if ⁵the places where the paint has not touched remain on the paper, it does not affect the continuity of the image, since the paints are absorbed and mixed with each other. From the pictorial and impactful possibilities of color to the freedom and complete k that an artist needs in painting

Only a person who is a true master of art can create such works, and only such works can educate new and new masters of art. For two thousand years, the Uzbek people have created and created such wonderful examples of the art of painting and applied art, which still fascinates people today with their high artistic skills and courtesy. But we cannot say that the works of fine art created in ancient times can be found on the territory of Uzbekistan ⁶in its full and whole form. Because due to the wars that our country was under and before the coverage of Russia, chinakkam art enthusiasts took them to their homeland and are now keeping them in their museums as works of historical art. Even so, the ancient monuments in Uzbekistan and the majestic Color Image Art that adorns them are of great importance for our Uzbek people. Chunk these works of art are important to us, whether in monuments, papers or stones. They are an argument that reminds us of our ancestors and makes them understand how great they are. Maybe these works of art are a simple image at first glance but are the basis for us and the ⁷next generation of history researchers. The more proud we are that we have such great norms, the less. Therefore, never let our Uzbekistan have an eye and independence will always be eternal.

⁵ Рўзинов, Б., Режабова, С., & Исмоилов, Ю. (2013). Қосимов А. Наманган вилояти маданий мероси. Наманган: Наманган.

⁶ Рўзинов, Б., Режабова, С., & Исмоилов, Ю. (2013). Қосимов А. Наманган вилояти маданий мероси. Наманган: Наманган

⁷ Рўзинов, Б., & Ражабова, С. (2006). Наманган вилояти маданий меросидан лавҳалар. Наманган нашриёти

It is impossible not to mention Genghis Ahmarov in the secret of the famous masters of the monumental decorative image. Inspired by the best examples of Oriental miniatures and the artistic heritage of the peoples of Central Asia, he created a number of amazing works (at the Ulugbek Museum in Samarkand, at the Alisher Navoi opera and Ballet Theater, at the Institute of Oriental Studies, at the Navoi metro station in Tashkent, at the palace of culture in Bukhara, etc.). In his works, Ahmarov artistically expresses the centuries-old aesthetic dreams of the Uzbek people and instills in the traditions of the art of ancient times the ideas of intensity and perseverance inherent in the present

The ancient monuments in Uzbekistan and the majestic art of painting decorating them are of great importance for our Uzbek people. These works of art are important to us, whether in monuments, papers or stones. They are an argument that reminds us of our ancestors and makes them understand how great they are. Maybe these works of art are a simple image at first glance but are the basis for us and the next generation of history researchers. The more proud we are that we have such great norms, the less. Therefore, never let our Uzbekistan have an eye and independence will always be eternal. Art with the help of its tools is not limited to the recognition of the world, the formation of spiritual qualities in a person, the expansion of conscious sensations, worldview, but also harmonizes such educational qualities as abilities and talents. On the basis of art, through artistic bodies, he finds expression in the surrounding world, like truthful depiction of everything that is happening in life. As noted above, it is not for nothing that in the works of painting, aesthetic features of a new form are also found in the work activity of a person in the future. It is no secret that within the works created on the territory of Uzbekistan from time immemorial, not only sculpture, samples of Applied Art, but also a large number of murals were noticed and captivated everyone with their charm. Although many of such unique works of art have disappeared, we have no doubt that the monumental painting works performed in the Afrosiab fortresses or Varakhsha fortresses are able to tell all of us about many secrets from the domestic life of their time. In Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, this art was built and developed in the era of the Middle Ages. During this period, the Houses of kings, nobles, palaces and temples were decorated with multi-shaped, movement-rich works of painting (Tuproqqal'a, Varakhsha, Balyktepa, Afrosiab, etc.), and during the Timurid and Timurid period, excellent samples of the majestic painting were also created. The Uzbek people are proud of their ancient high culture and art. This is clearly evidenced by archaeological excavations carried out on the territory of Uzbekistan. In particular, mural painting, sculptural works, applied art objects created at a high artistic level found in Varakhsha, Afrosiab, Khalchayon, Yulgaga'la, Balyktepa, Ayrtom, Dalvarzin Topa, Ajinatepa, Peshikkala and a number of other ancient cities, castles, temples are evidence of our opinion. The most ancient art samples on the territory of Uzbekistan indicate that the Uzbek ring has been a very ancient, cultural and art owner, and works have been created here at a high artistic level.

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Conclusion: in place of conclusion, it should be noted that today there are major reforms carried out by our Prism in the field of art. In particular, we can see the great attention that the scope of our 5 important initiatives has to do with art, and of course, as is one of such reforms. Of these, the effective organization of the subject of competent painting in accordance with the state educational standard in teaching, full-fledged explanation of student youth in practical and lecture classes with the course process is, of course, the task of the teacher.

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